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**Determinants of Reading Ability of Grade VI Pupils in
Tubod District, Division of Surigao del Norte:
Basis for An Intervention Program**

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Abstract

Reading is a fundamental skill that serves as the foundation for academic success and lifelong learning, making its development essential during the elementary years. However, limited local studies have comprehensively examined how pupil, parent, and teacher factors interact to influence the reading ability of Grade VI pupils, particularly in the Tubod District. This study investigated the determinants influencing the reading ability of Grade VI pupils in Tubod District, Division of Surigao del Norte, focusing on pupil-related factors (gender, reading habits), parental characteristics (monthly income, educational attainment), and teacher attributes (educational attainment, teaching experience). The study involved 170 Grade VI pupils, determined using Slovin's formula, and 11 reading teachers. Reading ability was assessed using the PHIL-IRI in both English and Filipino, while determinants were gathered through validated questionnaires.

Results revealed that only 34% of pupils were independent readers, while the majority were at the instructional level in both English and Filipino. Notably, 11% in Filipino and 12% in English were at the frustration level, indicating slow or struggling readers. Correlation analysis showed significant positive relationships between reading ability and monthly family income ($r = .43$), parental educational attainment, home and school reading support, teachers' educational attainment ($r = .70$), and teaching experience. Pupils from higher-income families and with more educated parents demonstrated stronger reading skills, attributed to increased availability of reading materials, internet access, and supportive home environments. Similarly, teachers with higher academic qualifications and longer teaching experience were linked to improved pupil performance.

Findings suggest that socioeconomic status, parental involvement, and teacher quality substantially influence reading ability. Most pupils with low reading levels came from low-income households with limited parental education, resulting in insufficient home reading support. It is recommended that parents create literacy-rich environments, provide reading resources, and encourage daily reading habits. Teachers are encouraged to pursue advanced education and training to strengthen reading instruction. Schools should address the lack of reading facilities and integrate structured interventions to foster independent reading skills. Strengthening collaboration among parents, teachers, and institutions is crucial in enhancing pupils' reading proficiency, forming a foundation for lifelong learning.

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Keywords: reading ability, Grade VI pupils, PHIL-IRI, parental involvement, socioeconomic status, teacher qualifications

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